

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Exact Analytical Solution of a Weighted Integral Geometry Problem

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Introduction. Reconstruction of an unknown function from its integral characteristics is one of the fundamental problems of computational mathematics, mathematical modeling, and inverse problem theory. Such problems arise naturally in a wide range of applied fields, including computer tomography, medical imaging, nondestructive testing, geophysics, and remote sensing. Within the framework of integral geometry, these problems are formulated as inverse problems for integral transforms defined on special families of curves or surfaces.

Of particular interest are weighted integral transforms associated with families of curves possessing prescribed geometric properties, such as parabolic curves. For such transforms, uniqueness theorems have been established, analytic inversion formulas have been derived, and stability estimates in Sobolev spaces have been obtained. The construction of inversion formulas is typically based on harmonic analysis techniques, in particular on the application of direct and inverse Fourier transforms.

Within the framework of weighted integral geometry on linear domains, the uniqueness of solutions for integral transforms defined over families of parabolic curves has been rigorously established. Considerable attention has been devoted to the derivation of inversion formulas, analytic solution representations, and stability estimates in Sobolev spaces. These inversion formulas fundamentally rely on the application of both direct and inverse Fourier transforms. As demonstrated in [1], the theory of integral geometry is closely related to representation theory of Lie groups, inverse boundary value problems for differential equations, and various practical applications, including tomographic imaging.

For different families of broken lines and surfaces with specific geometric properties, uniqueness theorems, stability estimates, and analytical inversion formulas for weighted integral transforms have been obtained. Problems involving weighted families of parabolic curves have likewise been thoroughly investigated [2]. The moderately ill-posed character of such problems, the uniqueness of solutions within classes of smooth compactly supported functions, and the derivation of stable inversion procedures based on Fourier methods are examined in detail in [3, 4].

Statement of the problem. Consider the following problem

$$\int_{(x,y)} g(x, \xi) u(\xi, \eta) ds = f(x, y) \quad (1)$$

here

$$g(x, \xi, y, \eta) = a_0 + a_1(y - \eta) + a_2(y - \eta)^2, \quad (x, y) = (x, y) : |x - \xi| = y - \eta$$

The considered integral problem belongs to the class of inverse problems for Fredholm integral equations of the first kind and is ill-posed in the sense of Hadamard. This means

that for arbitrary input data $f(x, y)$ a solution may not exist, and even if it exists, neither uniqueness nor stability is guaranteed. In particular, small perturbations in the right-hand side of the equation may lead to significant changes in the reconstructed function.

Equation (1) can be equivalently rewritten in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \int_0^y (a_0 + a_1(y - \eta) + a_2(y - \eta)^2) u(x - (y - \eta), \eta) d\eta \\ & + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \int_0^y (a_0 + a_1(y - \eta) + a_2(y - \eta)^2) u(x + (y - \eta), \eta) d\eta = f(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

We apply the Fourier transform with respect to the variable to both sides of equation (2), which yields:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^y \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta) (a_0 + a_1(y - \eta) + a_2(y - \eta)^2) \cos(\lambda(y - \eta)) d\eta = \\ & = \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty e^{-\mu\eta} e^{i\mu\tau} \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta) \cos(\lambda\tau) (a_0 + a_1\tau + a_2\tau^2) d\tau d\eta = \\ & = \int_0^\infty e^{i\mu\eta} \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta) d\eta \int_0^\infty e^{-i\mu\tau} (a_0 + a_1\tau + a_2\tau^2) \cos(\lambda\tau) d\tau. \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\hat{f}(\lambda, \mu) = \hat{u}(\lambda, \mu) I(\lambda, \mu)$$

where $I(\lambda, \mu) = \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-i\mu\tau} (a_0 + a_1\tau + a_2\tau^2) \cos(\lambda\tau) d\tau$

As a result, we obtain

$$\tilde{u}(\lambda, \mu) = \frac{\sqrt{2} \hat{f}(\lambda, \mu)}{\left(\frac{ia_0\mu}{\lambda^2\tau^2 - \mu^2} - a_1 \frac{\mu^2 + \lambda^2\tau^2}{(\lambda^2\tau^2 - \mu^2)^2} + a_2 \frac{2i\mu(-\mu^2 - 3\lambda^2\tau^2)}{(\lambda^2\tau^2 - \mu^2)^3} \right)}$$

Taking the inverse Fourier transform with respect to μ and λ , we arrive at the following expression:

$$u(x, y) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sqrt{2} \hat{f}(\lambda, \mu) (\lambda^2\tau^2 - \mu^2)^3 e^{-i\mu y - i\lambda x}}{ia_0\mu(\lambda^2\tau^2 - \mu^2) - a_1(\lambda^2\tau^2 - \mu^2)^2 - 2ia_2\mu(\mu^2 + 3\lambda^2\tau^2)} d\mu d\lambda$$

The numerical evaluation of the obtained integral representation is associated with substantial difficulties arising from both the analytical structure of the inversion kernel and the properties of the Fourier transforms involved. These difficulties are intrinsic to the inverse nature of the problem and reflect its moderately ill-posed character.

A major source of instability is the presence of singular spectral factors of the form $(\lambda^2\tau^2 - \mu^2)^{-k}$, which appear in the denominator of the inversion formula. These factors generate poles in the spectral domain along the critical manifolds $\mu = \pm\lambda\tau$, where the denominator vanishes. In the neighbourhood of these points, the integrand exhibits rapid growth and strong oscillatory behaviour, which makes the numerical integration highly sensitive to perturbations in the data. As a result, even small measurement errors

or discretization inaccuracies in the right-hand side function $f(x, y)$ may lead to large deviations in the reconstructed solution.

Another fundamental difficulty is related to the amplification of high-frequency components in the Fourier domain. Since the inversion formula involves division by small spectral values, the high-frequency noise contained in the measured data is significantly magnified. This effect is characteristic of inverse problems for integral equations of the first kind and represents a manifestation of their ill-posedness in the sense of Hadamard. In practice, this leads to spurious oscillations in the reconstructed function and to the loss of physical interpretability of the numerical solution.

For these reasons, direct numerical evaluation of the inversion integral is impractical without the use of regularization techniques. In order to obtain a stable and physically meaningful reconstruction, it is necessary to introduce spectral filtering or Tikhonov-type regularization, which suppresses the influence of high-frequency noise and prevents the blow-up of the solution near the singular spectral sets. Such approaches make it possible to balance stability and accuracy and provide a reliable numerical implementation of the analytical inversion formula.

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